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Large scale interventions in Boston's Back Bay/ 1950 - present. A self-correcting Modernist Urbanism

Introduction

1. No American city has a more traditional cultural dynamic, smaller scale, and in the parts of this city planned in the 19th century, greater traditional continuity in its urban programs than Boston. Yet, it merits a place on the agenda of the Modern City Facing the Future, for it was the site of several significant post World War II urban interventions by noted modernists. While the most notorious was the Government Center (Master Plan by I.M. Pei, 1959), a conventional urban renewal project created on a *tabula rasa* leveled for this purpose; between 1963 and 1972 there were also two successive, independently conceived, interventions in Boston's Back Bay. If taken together, they present an excellent example of what we call an ameliorative, self-correcting modernist urbanism. In the Back Bay, we will argue, little built 19th century fabric was disturbed, relatively few people were displaced, and most importantly for our argument, modernists replanned the traditional city while recognizing the necessity of taking that city into account. In an interesting reversal of the typical post-war American pattern, they departed from 20th Century urban models to follow a strategy of urban intervention that was adaptive and aggregative. Each project responded not only to predecessors, but also to the existing urban tissue, following a strategy that led to moderation

and accommodation, and thus, to a form of urban conservation.

2. The Prudential Center (original plan under the title of Back Bay Center, Walter Gropius and TAC; 1956; expanded by Luckman, Pereira, and Belluschi, 1959-1965), or as its 52 - storey tower is known in Boston, the Pru, served as the catalyst for the subsequent projects, the Christian Science Center (I.M. Pei and Araldo Cossutta, 1963-1972, which we will call the CSC) and the John Hancock Tower (Henry Cobb of I. M. Pei and Partners, 1967-1973).

The architects of the CSC and Hancock sought to respond to the pre-existing conditions and to the disruptions in scale introduced by the Prudential Center. Although they kept to fundamental modernist principles, Cossuta and Cobb both resisted and corrected the fundamentally anti-urban modernist forms that the Pru had introduced. The overall result was, to coin a neologism, a *re-conceptualized modernism*, that is, an ameliorative modernist intervention that conserved Boston's traditional urbanity in a rare instance of a successful adjustment of modern urbanism to the needs of a city with deep historical associations and a specific regional identity.

Our analysis will proceed chronologically. We will describe the self-correcting strategies, show how they were successfully employed in the development of this area, and how the modernism employed display *extraordinary generosity and responsiveness* in responding to a highly particular urban condition.

3. The site for all three projects is a triangular zone between the Back Bay and the South End, both cohesively planned 19th century neighborhoods. Its eastern, downtown-facing apex is Copley Square, home to the national architectural treasures of Trinity Church (H. H. Richardson, 1873-1879), the Beaux-Arts Boston Public Library (McKim, Mead, and White, 1881-1888; Charles McKim, designer) and other prestigious buildings. Its western base on Massachusetts Avenue was the complex of building surrounding the Mother Church of the Church of Christ Scientist, a Protestant sect founded in Boston in the 19th Century. Its dome had long defined the low, mainly domestic, Back Bay skyline. The interstitial triangle between the two disconnected street grids was primarily filled with railroad yards, and these were surrounded by a relatively small number of streets of housing and shops.

4. Although the triangle is defined at its extremes by two groups of monumental buildings, for the Mother Church has two important civic neighbors (Symphony and Horticultural Halls), neither the eastern apex nor the western base constituted fully resolved monumental public spaces. This situation was far more serious in the case of Copley Square, home to several of the cultural and religious institutions that had defined the city's identity when it was the famed "Athens of America."

5. The railroad yards were the first area targeted for new developments by Boston's city planners when the city sought to revive its economically stagnant fortunes through the initiation of the large-scale urban interventions officially entitled the "New Boston." To this area was assigned a new headquarters for the Prudential Insurance Company, a major local financial institution and employer, along with apartment buildings and shopping facilities. The Christian Science Church subsequently planned its expansion on the substantial land holdings it possessed to the south and west of the Pru tower; and finally the John Hancock Insurance Company planned a tower to be sited on the lot abutting the southeast corner of Copley Square.

The Prudential Center

1. The original Gropius plan for the Back Bay Center, already a project for a fully modernist city within the city, was expanded into the Prudential Center, composed of the Pru tower, a secondary office tower, four mid-rise slab residential blocks, a hotel, two major department stores and a gallery of smaller shops. Separated by a boundary access road that completely divorced it from the Back Bay grid, the Pru Center exacerbated the separateness of the original interstitial zone and added other elements of urban isolation. Its designer, Charles Luckman, acted in conformity with that part of the modernist ethos that was fundamentally anti-urban at heart.

2. Even before its construction was complete, the Pru provoked several inter-related reactions in the local design community, thereby inadvertently initiating the subsequent self-correcting impulse that, we argue, came to characterize the subsequent large-scale architectural interventions in this area. The design community demanded that any future development create a dialogue with the existing, mainly 19th century city, in which the very few high-rise buildings were clustered in the financial district to the east (Sturgis, cited by Cobb, 2000)¹ Recognizing that the Prudential Center had failed to engage its context, either urbanistically or architecturally, they turned to Kevin Lynch's *The Image of the City* (Lynch, 1959)² and to Lynch, himself, who was a professor at MIT. They argued that legibility was needed if a city was to be both recognizable by its inhabitants, as Lynch had shown in his book. They proposed that all future high-rise buildings projected for the Back Bay be placed along what they called the "high spine," a jagged line that would connect the Pru to the old financial core of the city to the east, where new towers were being planned. Thus, the acceptance in Boston of the "high spine" idea as a guiding principle meant that the still undeveloped parts of the interstitial zone of the former rail

yards would henceforth be developed in keeping with Lynch's ideas of a legible image of the city. The foundations for the self-correcting process were laid.

Christian Science Center

1. The design for the CSC to the south and west of the Prudential Center was the next step in the self-correcting process. The original Christian Science Church buildings consisted of a Romanesque revival Mother Church (1904, Franklin J. Welch) with Neo-Renaissance additions, including the signature dome (1908, Brigham and Beman), and the Publishing House (*idem*, 1930). Executed entirely in gray granite and a buff-colored Indiana limestone, the buildings have a monumental presence unlike that of the more traditional Bostonian limestone trimmed brick architecture, such as that of the adjacent Beau- Arts Symphony and Horticultural Halls.

2. In 1963, Araldo Cossutta, who, in association with I. M. Pei and Partners, was engaged as the principal architect and master planner for the new Church complex, concluded that the most effective way for the Church to assert its physical presence within a vertically expanding city was to effectively command the horizontal plane. Making the one gesture that no profit-driven privately-financed project could afford, he planned the new buildings around a vast, but well-defined and accessible, plaza, with a reflecting pool at its center (Cossutta, 2000).³ His master plan grouped a Sunday School, a colonnaded library, and a 28-story administration tower around this space. The tower was counterpoised to the dome of the church building across the open space and was designed to be of sufficient dimension to continue to clearly mark the position and importance of the Church within the physical fabric of the city. The placement of the elements of the complex conformed to the principles advocated by Lynch, with the location of the tower following the jagged line advocated by the proponents of the High Spine.

In sum, self-correction was realized: the CSC plaza made a compensatory gesture for the urban and spatial disruptions caused by the Prudential Center, even as the monumentality of the new ensemble created a new representation of the Church in relation to Boston. Moreover, the CSC retained its position in the 'image of the city,' creating resistance and balance to the incursion of the Pru.

3. Each of the elements of the CSC is composed in a classically modernist, balanced, asymmetrical fashion, and each element is dependent upon the others to render the composition whole. At its southern edge, the plaza opens on to and begins to engage the South End across Huntington Avenue, while the northern edge (which faces the precinct of the

Pru) is defined by the most architecturally distinctive element of the complex, a linear, colonnaded structure based loosely upon Le Corbusier's High Court at Chandigarh.

The colonnade functions as a visual screen between the Pru and the heart of the CSC, extending the long block of the 1930's Beaux-Arts Publishing House to effectively define the great space between the Mother Church and its focus on the distant Copley Square. At the center of the plaza is a long reflecting pool between the colonnade and the street. This space connects the tower, at its southeast corner, with the Mother Church and the Publishing House, which anchors the northwest corner of the site. The eastern end of the pool opens toward the edge of the Prudential Center and Copley Square, while the western end terminates in the Sunday School building that, by presenting a curved elevation to the pool, redirects the space into the forecourt of the Mother Church in true modernist fashion. Across the southern and western boundaries of the site, Cossutta and the Church sought to extend their vision into the community through the construction of both linear and mid-rise tower apartment blocks, and a hotel. The most effective of these is the Church Park Apartments (TAC, 1965), animated at street level with an arcade of shops. They form a 1,000 foot linear foil to the highly articulated west front of the Mother Church and its extended forecourt and draw the earlier Beaux-Arts civic monuments of Symphony and Horticultural Hall into the composition.

4. As a result, the monumental statement of CSC reaches out at its edges to engage the neighborhoods by selectively defining the perimeter through its placement of its objects (Tower and Sunday School), wall (Colonnade) and the empty landscaped plane (Plaza – the void at its heart). The image-making intention and scale of its elements notwithstanding, the CSC remains a non-assertive, quietly monumental, precinct of distinguished, but ultimately non-polemical, architecture. Self-correction created a significant reconceptualization of the classic modernist urban model.

5. Moreover, Cossutta picked up the original palette of materials and made it contemporary through his use of a vocabulary of the refined cast-in-place concrete that was already becoming the hallmark material of the Pei office. We conclude that the introduction of a sympathetic, coherent, contemporary monumentality in an asymmetrical, harmoniously colored, anti-historicist composition clearly signaled a willingness on the part of the architect to recognize that his engagement with the surrounding areas demanded a new approach to modernist urbanism. It is significant for the contemporary trajectory of American architecture that Cossutta, an

Italian born in Yugoslavia, would critically overlay his modernism with a sensitivity to context similar to that which Colin Rowe was beginning to articulate in his writings and to his students at Cornell University. Like Rowe, he would have been familiar with the graphic patterning of the traditional European city. He certainly appears to have been ready to incorporate this sensibility into his work. His strategy foreshadows the growth of interest in contextualism in the 1970's.

The John Hancock Tower

1. While the Pei office was still completing the designs for the Christian Science Center, partner Henry Cobb was engaged by the John Hancock Mutual Insurance Company to design a new headquarters on land directly adjacent to Copley Square. The Hancock tower was a highly controversial project, both within the city and in architectural circles across the United States. Unlike the Pru, which had been constructed on an virtually barren urban site, the Hancock, a building of great height and bulk, was planned to be constructed immediately adjacent to the great nineteenth and early twentieth century monuments of Copley Square – a gesture that even in this time of the relative acceptance of tall buildings in the context of older cities was initially seen as an affront to its urban setting. Hancock essentially had the zoning laws of the City of Boston rewritten to accommodate their needs for this project and their intention to build taller (and with a larger floor plate) than the Prudential tower.⁴ Cobb, a native Bostonian who was highly sensitive to the history, problems and constraints of this site, developed a strategy that negotiated between these inflexible demands and the historic architecture of Copley Square in the immediate proximity and that took into account the fact that these civic monuments are commanding but delicate in scale and articulation. He sought to create an architecture with urban consequences, or a kind of virtual urbanism, that achieved self-correction by at least partially acknowledging the context without, however, deferring to it.

2. He approached the difference between new and old and between building and context through a series of inversions that ultimately came to define the building. He gave the 60 – storey skyscraper the shape of a rhombus and clad it in undifferentiated flat-plate mirrored glass of maximum dimension, thereby creating a skin with minimal articulation and maximal reflectivity. The rhombus inflects towards the apse of Trinity Church, and the geometry of the Back Bay is therefore reflected on its narrow face. This façade is in turn further dematerialized by a full-height notch cleaving the elevation that reduces the apparent bulk of the building relative to the Back

Bay. The broad elevation is placed perpendicular to the hypotenuse of the interstitial triangle. It thus reflects the brutality of the neighboring incursions into this zone formed by a depressed 8 lane regional highway, the Prudential Center, and finally the Hancock itself, while bluntly acknowledging the old grid of the South End.

3. Modernist in its single mindedness, relentlessness, scalelessness and unapologetic autonomy, the Hancock also embraces minimalism, as Raphael Moneo has pointed out (Moneo, 1989, p.177).⁵ This move, very much of its time, dematerializes the behemoth and makes it stark and simple). Yet, because its sheer mass unequivocally announces the power and anonymity of corporate wealth, its *modernism* nonetheless overwhelms and displaces Trinity Church, the representation of the culture of traditional Boston and becomes, through reflectivity, a literal enactment of *modernization*.

4. Cobb's initial design sought fuller self-correction. He foresaw a substantial addition to the public realm through the construction of a low-rise cultural center on Hancock property opposite the tower site. This center would have made a programmatic and formal contribution to the public realm by opening onto a new public plaza. This would have established a relationship with Trinity Church and Copley Square. The existing apse of Trinity Church, which Cobb perceives as the true intended focus of Richardson's design, would have created a pivot point between the old and new plazas (Cobb, 2000).⁶

5. Not only did the failure to execute this design compromise the nonetheless still considerable power of the architectural gesture of the tower, it blunted Cobb's ameliorative intentions. The resulting urban form would have interwoven the new and old in a manner similar to that of CSC's plaza's response to the forecourt of the Mother Church. The rotation of the public square relative to the normative geometry of the Back Bay and to the inflection of the tower would have heightened the legibility of the plaza as it develops off of the geometry of Copley Square and Trinity Church, thus making the setting of the tower itself more legible. The building would have been seen as a keystone, presenting the minimum possible exposure to the historic space, while absorbing, reflecting and reconciling the considerable architectural tensions that converge on this site. Thus Cobb would have successfully reconceptualized, on the urban scale, the modernist approach to the problematic design of this site.

6. Today, the tower is a stunning presence on the Boston skyline, seeming to dematerialize and to reform with every change in the light. At a distance, it calls attention to its own *mutability* and, in doing so, to the fundamental intrusiveness of the Pruden-

tial Center. At street level, however, it continues to make evident the *immutability* of the concentration of contemporary financial power and the ambiguity inherent in the relationship of the corporation to the city. Neither the 1960's landscaping of Copley Square by Hideo Sasaki nor any of the several subsequent landscape designs in a more post-modern mode have mitigated this fact. But aside from this disclosure of the nature of modernization, itself an inevitable fact of any tall building, the Hancock generates an antidote to its own generic universalism through the use of void, dematerialization and difference.

Conclusion

1. The CSC and the Hancock were at least in part generated as contextual responses to both the 19th century city and to the major mid-century interventions of the "island" of the Prudential Center but without renouncing the essential modernism of their urban and architectural qualities. In turn, these interventions have had a sanguine effect upon subsequent development in the area. The CSC enters into direct and vibrant dialogue with the major cultural buildings and residential blocks along the Massachusetts Avenue edge. The Hancock Tower has had a catalytic effect by inspiring the largely successful effort to make Copley Square a truly public space, and, as we have shown, continues to attenuate the overwhelming presence of the Pru and the other more recent smaller towers implanted in its precinct. The effect of this self-correction is a reconceptualized modernism and a form of modernist urban conservation.

2. This area continues to evolve: development pressures, many accompanied by a nostalgic desire for "traditional" appearances, are enormous and have prompted interventions of questionable merit. However, the strength of the initial impulse—the power of Hancock's dematerialized solid and the great void and the deferent, yet monumental, modernist aesthetic of the CSC; with its ability to catalyze the successful transformation of the surrounding neighborhoods—form an ameliorative approach to modernism that merits attention as an urban model for the modernist city facing the future.

Fig. 1 – Aerial View of Boston, 1986. The Back Bay and “High Spine” development are visible on the right moving toward downtown in the center.
Photo: Alex MacLean for Landslides, 1986.

Fig. 2 – Aerial Detail of Back Bay with Christian Science Center, Prudential Center and Hancock from right to center, respectively.
Photo: Alex MacLean for Landslides, 1986.

Fig. 3 – Christian Science Center, with Prudential Center to the upper right.
Photo: Alex MacLean for Landslides, 1981.

Fig. 4 – Christian Science Center from the east: From the left - Administration Tower, Sunday School, Mother Church and Colonnade, 1976.
Photo: Pei, Cobb, Freed and Partners

Fig. 5 – Christian Science Center: Plaza looking.
Photo: David Fixler

Fig. 6 – Christian Science Center: Colonnade from south, 1976.
Photo: Pei Cobb, Freed and Partners

Fig. 7 – Christian Science Center and Church Park Apartments (linear block at bottom), 1986.
Photo: Alex MacLean for Landslides

Fig. 8 – Christian Science Center. Forecourt of Mother Church with Sunday School and Horticultural Hall, 2000.
Photo: David Fixler

Fig. 9 – John Hancock Tower, 1976.
Photo: Pei Cobb, Freed and Partners

Fig. 10 – Hancock Tower site relative to Copley Square, 1976.
Photo: Pei Cobb, Freed and Partners

Fig. 11 – Henry Cobb sketch and notes on the siting of the Hancock Tower, 1967.
Photo: Pei Cobb, Freed and Partners

Fig. 12 – Model of the Hancock Tower with proposed plaza to the east, 1967.
Model and Photo: Pei Cobb, Freed and Partners

Fig. 13 – Hancock from west displaying the property of self reflection, 1976.
Photo: Alex MacLean for Landslides

Fig. 14 – Hancock Tower from the 19th Century Back Bay.
Photo: Pei Cobb, Freed and Partners

Fig. 15 – Hancock Tower in context from across the Charles River, 1976
Photo: Pei Cobb, Freed and Partners

Fig. 15 – Hancock Tower with reflection of Trinity Church, 1976
Photo: Pei Cobb, Freed and Partners

NOTES

¹ Interviews with Henry Cobb of Pei, Cobb, Freed and Partners, March 16, 2000 and Robert Sturgis, May 23, 2000. Robert Sturgis is an architect who chaired a committee of the Boston Society of Architects that proposed the idea of the High Spine.

² Lynch, Kevin (1959): *The Image of the City*, Cambridge, MIT Press

³ Interview with Araldo Cossutta, March 16, 2000

⁴ Hancock threatened to move their operations to Chicago if the City would not comply with their request.

⁵ Moneo, Raphael (1989): 'Concerning the Hancock Tower'. *Harvard Architecture Review* 7 Cambridge.

⁶ Interview with Henry Cobb, op.cit.

KEYWORDS

Boston, BackBay: Christian Science Center, John Hancock Tower M. Pei & Partners, Post-War American Architecture and Urbanism, Cobb, Henry, Cossutta, Araldo

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